

SOCIOCULTURAL DIFFERENCES IN FAMILY DISCOURSE IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE FICTION BOOKS

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Annotation: This article explores how the culture of a particular place or region greatly influences its literature and has an effect on a character's mental setup in terms of their moral, intellectual, and psychological personality development. This research has taken different novels from different parts of the world, which were written in the English language. Through its examination of certain novels, this article portrays how culture influences every aspect of life and explores of sociocultural differences in family discourse in English language fiction books.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola ma'lum bir joy yoki mintaqaning madaniyati uning adabiyotiga qanday ta'sir qilishini va uning axloqiy, intellektual va psixologik shaxsiyatini rivojlantirish nuqtai nazaridan uning ruhiy holatiga qanday ta'sir qilishini o'rganadi. Ushbu tadqiqot dunyoning turli burchaklaridan ingliz tilida yozilgan turli xil romanlarni oldi. Ba'zi romanlarni o'rganish orqali ushbu maqola madaniyat hayotning har bir jabhasiga qanday ta'sir qilishini tasvirlaydi va ingliz tilidagi badiiy asarlarida oilaviy nutqdagi ijtimoiy-madaniy farqlarni o'rganadi.

Fiction books have long been a reflection of society, providing insights into various aspects of human life, including family dynamics. The exploration of sociocultural differences in family discourse within English language fiction books offers a fascinating lens through which to examine the diversity and complexities of family structures, values, and norms across different cultures and societies.

Family is a fundamental societal institution, and its portrayal in fiction books allows readers to gain a deeper understanding of how social and cultural factors shape interpersonal relationships within families. English language fiction books have depicted a wide range of family units, from the traditional nuclear family to extended families, single-parent households, same-sex parents, and blended families. Each of these configurations reflects the unique sociocultural context in which a particular story is set.

One prominent aspect of family discourse in fiction books is the cultural expectation of filial piety, particularly within Asian cultures. Works like Amy Tan's "The Joy Luck Club" and Lisa See's "Snow Flower and the Secret Fan" delve

into the complexities of mother-daughter relationships and the intergenerational conflicts that arise from different cultural values. Readers gain insights into the expectations and responsibilities placed on individuals within the family unit, as well as the significance of maintaining harmony and respect within these relationships. Another significant sociocultural difference in family discourse is the contrasting role and portrayal of women within different societies. Fiction books written in the English language, such as Jane Austen's "Pride and Prejudice" and Charlotte Bronte's "Jane Eyre," offer insightful narratives about the expectations and limitations placed on women during the Victorian era. These novels shed light on the societal pressure for women to conform to prescribed gender roles, highlighting the struggle for independence and agency within the confines of societal expectations.

Furthermore, the role of the extended family plays heavily in family discourse throughout various cultures. In African American literature, for example, Toni Morrison's "Beloved" explores the impact of slavery on family bonds and the enduring strength of communal ties. The extended family, sometimes referred to as "kinship network," provides a support system beyond the nuclear family, addressing the collective responsibilities and interconnectedness prevalent within African American communities.

Moreover, sociocultural differences can also be seen in the depiction of alternative family structures such as single-parent households, same-sex parents, and blended families. For instance, Jodi Picoult's "My Sister's Keeper" presents a complex picture of a family dealing with the challenges of having a child with a life-threatening illness, while Lionel Shriver's "We Need to Talk About Kevin" explores the breakdown of a family following a high school shooting. These works depict the adversity families face within non-traditional structures while challenging societal norms and values. Sociocultural differences in family discourse within English language fiction books expand our understanding of family dynamics beyond our own cultural boundaries. They allow us to gain insights into the diverse experiences, values, and challenges faced by families across different cultures, eras, and social contexts. By immersing ourselves in these stories, we develop empathy and an appreciation for the complexities of family relationships that transcend sociocultural differences.

In conclusion, the exploration of sociocultural differences in family discourse in English language fiction books offers a rich tapestry of narratives that capture the diversity and complexities of family life. From filial piety to the struggles of women in society, the importance of extended families, and the challenges of alternative family structures, these stories provide invaluable insights into the diverse sociocultural contexts in which families thrive. By delving into these narratives, readers gain a deeper understanding of the intersectionality of familial relationships, fostering empathy, and appreciation for the multifaceted nature of family dynamics.

References:

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